

Screening of *Enterobacteriaceae* with antimicrobial resistance from cold, home-made beverages sold in selected food stalls of Dasmariñas City, Cavite

Daniel D. Geda¹, Marigold O. Uba²

¹Biology Department, St. Dominic College of Asia, Bacoor City, Cavite, Philippines

²School of Health Science Professions, St. Dominic College of Asia, Bacoor City, Cavite, Philippines

*Corresponding author

Abstract

Cold street beverages are popular choice of drinks in the Philippines due to its convenience and low cost. However, bacteria present in the beverages can cause public health issues. Antibiotic resistance is a growing global concern which makes infections more dangerous and harder to cure. This paper intended to isolate and identify the Enterobacteriaceae found in the cold street beverages sold on Dasmariñas Bagong Bayan, Dasmariñas, Cavite as well as determine if the isolated organisms are resistant to different kinds of antibiotics. A total of 15 isolates were collected in six (6) different kinds of beverages. Out of the 15 isolates, there were nine (9) different species identified using API20E with the majority of the isolates coming from the Enterobacteriaceae family. All 15 isolates were tested for antibiotic resistance using disc diffusion. There were four out of 15 (4/15, 27%) that can be considered as multi-drug resistance. The isolates were identified using API20E as E. cloacae (S1-IS1), R. planticola (S3-IS1A), R. planticola (S4-IS2), and A. baumannii / calcoaceticus (S5-IS1A). In conclusion, it is risky to consume cold street beverages due to the presence of antibiotic resistant bacteria. Further studies may be done to increase the knowledge regarding the risk of contracting infections from consuming cold drink beverages.

Keywords: *Enterobacteriaceae; cold street beverage; antibiotic resistance; multi-drug resistance.*

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Introduction

Street foods are appreciated for many things. It is convenient, it has unique flavors, and it can also be important in the nutrition of the population (Rane, 2011). Moreover, it is described by the Food and Agriculture Organization as “*ready-to-eat foods and beverages sold and sometimes prepared in public places, notably streets.*” Street foods have become popular not only because it is convenient and affordable, but also because it is one of the main sources of livelihood of people (Buted & Ylagan, 2014). However, the convenience of street food also has its drawbacks. This is due to the lack of awareness of most street vendors regarding proper hygiene procedures and proper food preparation and management (Hilario, 2015). Moreover, street foods pose major health risk to the public due to microbial contamination, lack of infrastructure and services, as well as difficulty in the regulation of the operation of street food vendors because of its diverse, mobile and temporary nature (Rane, 2011; WHO, 2011).

One of the common microbial contaminations in food is *Escherichia coli* and its presence is already an indicative of fecal contamination (Gelsomino et al., 2002) which is due to poor hygienic practices during the preparation, handling, as well as insufficient equipment for reheating and storage (Tambekar et al., 2011). The Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) described *E. coli* as gram-negative bacteria that can be found normally in the intestines of people and animals. Some are mostly harmless and an

important part of a healthy human intestinal tract, but some strains are pathogenic (Hansen, 2021). The pathogenic strains that are usually associated with foodborne outbreaks include: Enterotoxigenic *Escherichia coli* (ETEC) and Shiga toxin-producing *E. coli* (STEC). Transmission of these bacteria is due to consumption of contaminated food or drinks.

The infection of pathogenic *E. coli* can be controlled by the different antibiotics prescribed by doctors. The real danger is when the pathogens have antimicrobial resistance to drugs. Antimicrobial resistance is the ability of microorganisms to nullify the effects of drugs. It prevents the antibiotic from killing or inhibiting the growth of bacteria (Dadgostar, 2019). The emergence of antimicrobial resistance strains of bacteria is a risk in present human and animal medicine. It is suspected that the frequent use of antimicrobial substances is the cause for the acquisition of resistance for different bacteria (WHO, 2011).

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the study was to isolate Enterobacteriaceae from beverages sold from randomly selected food stalls in Dasmariñas City and determined its antimicrobial sensitivity to selected antibiotics. Specifically, the study aimed to:

1. Isolate Enterobacteriaceae from cold, homemade beverages sold in selected food stalls in Dasmariñas City, Cavite;
2. Identify the isolated Enterobacteriaceae using API 20E; and
3. Determine the antibiotic sensitivity of the isolates using disk diffusion method

Significance of the Study

Considering the increase of microbial contamination among food preparation as well as the emergence of antibiotic resistant bacterial strains isolated from these samples, the study can provide additional data on this especially on a local setting. Antibiotic resistance is important since it can increase hospital costs, duration of the disease, and mortality rates. The World Health Organization released a report in 2018 that said serious bacterial infections have a high level of resistance to antibiotics in both high-income and low-income countries (Lindmeier, 2018). Without effective antimicrobials for prevention and treatment of infections, common diseases are becoming harder to treat and some medical procedures such as organ transplant and major surgeries are becoming more dangerous. The organization also reported in 2017 that the world is running out of antibiotics since most of the drugs currently in development are modifications of existing antibiotics and are only short-term solutions (Scutti, 2017). There have been no outbreaks of any water-borne diseases in the sampling site so the study can give information if an outbreak may be possible.

Scope and Limitation

The study was limited by the following scope and limitations:

1. Samples considered for collected are cold, homemade beverages sold in Dasmariñas Bagong Bayan, Dasmariñas City, Cavite;
2. Two different stalls were sampled, and three cold, homemade beverages were collected for each stall;
3. API 20E System was used for the identification of all bacterial isolates;
4. Kirby-Bauer disk diffusion method was the only method used to test the antibiotic sensitivity of the isolates; and
5. The only antibiotics used during testing were the following: Third Generation Cephalosporins: Ceftazidime (CAZ) and Ceftriaxone (CRO). Carbapenem: Ertapenem (ETP) and Meropenem

(MRP). Phenicol: Chloramphenicol (C). Aminoglycoside: Gentamicin (GM). Penicillin: Ampicillin (AM). Folate pathway inhibitor: Trimethoprim-Sulfamethoxazole (SXT). Tetracycline: Tetracycline (T). β – lactam / β – lactamase inhibitor: Amoxicillin-clavulanate (AMC)

Methodology

Collection of Samples

Samples were collected last October 23, 2018 in a selected site at Dasmarinas Bagong Bayan, Dasmariñas, Cavite. The said site is near Dasmariñas Elementary School, Immaculate Concepcion Church, and Dasmariñas City Hall. Two food stalls were considered for collection and three beverages for each stall were used for the sample. The two sample sites were 10 meters away from each other. The plastic cups provided by the stalls were used as a container for the collected beverages. The cups were immediately sealed in a plastic bag and placed inside a cooler for transportation. The samples were transported to the Biology Laboratory of St. Dominic College of Asia, where it was processed immediately.

Isolation and Purification

From the collected samples, 0.1 mL from each sample was inoculated into an Eosin Methylene Blue (EMB) agar plate using spread plate method. This was then incubated at 37°C for 24 hours. After incubation, all plates that exhibit colonial growth were further subcultured into Nutrient Agar (NA) plates until similar or distinct colonies were observed.

Gram Staining

The gram staining reaction of the bacterial isolates were determined before using API 20E as a confirmatory test for the purity of the isolates. Fresh cultures of isolates were used for staining. The isolates were inoculated on a drop of sterile distilled water placed on the glass slide. After the sample was heat fixed, crystal violet was used and let to stand for 30 seconds. The crystal violet was rinsed with sterile distilled water and the slide was covered with Gram's iodine and was left for one minute. Afterwards, it was rinsed again. 95% ethanol was used as a decolorizer for 15 seconds and it was rinsed with sterile distilled water. Safranin was added and left to stand for one minute and rinsed with sterile distilled water. The slide was blot dried and observed under oil immersion. All isolates were gram negative; all of it were stained pink to red when it was observed.

Oxidase Test

After Gram staining, oxidase test was used on the isolates, since Enterobacteriaceae are oxidase negative and oxidase test results are needed for the API 20E. New cultures of isolates were used in the oxidase test. The isolates were inoculated on a drop of sterile distilled water on a sterile glass slide. Drops of the oxidase reagent was added to the inoculum and it was mixed. All isolates were oxidase negative as indicated by the lack of the formation of color blue after adding the reagent.

API 20E System

The API 20E System is a standardized and miniaturized version of the biochemical tests used for identification of Enterobacteriaceae and other gram-negative bacteria. It is a strip that contains 20 chambers that consists of a microtube, and a depression called cupule. The cupules contain the dehydrated substrates used for the biochemical tests and was rehydrated by adding bacterial saline suspension. After the microtubes were inoculated with the isolates, it was then incubated at 37°C for 24 hours. The strip was read by noting the color changes after adding reagents. The identity of the unknown bacterium is achieved by determining a seven-digit profile index number and consulting the API 20E Profile Recognition.

Antibiotic Susceptibility Test

The isolated Enterobacteriaceae from the collected samples was subjected to antibiotic susceptibility testing following the Kirby-Bauer Disc Diffusion Method. The different antibiotics that were used for testing include the following: Third Generation Cephalosporins: Ceftazidime (CAZ) and Ceftriaxone (CRO); Carbapenem: Ertapenem (ETP) and Meropenem (MRP); Phenicol: Chloramphenicol (C); Aminoglycoside: Gentamicin (GM); Penicillin: Ampicillin (AM); Folate pathway inhibitor: Trimethoprim-Sulfamethoxazole (SXT); Tetracycline: Tetracycline (TE); and β – lactam / β – lactamase inhibitor: Amoxicillin-clavulanate (AMC). The antibiotics used were based on Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute 2018 according to its class. Before the disk diffusion assay, bacterial isolates were standardized using 0.5 McFarland (0.05 mL of 1.175% Barium Chloride and 9.95 mL of Hydrogen Sulphate). Mueller-Hinton Agar (MHA) was freshly prepared and used for the assay. The standardized inoculum was incubated into MHA plate using cotton swab by streaking on the surface of the entire agar through rotating the plate 60 degrees after each streak. The inoculated plate was left to dry for a few minutes before adding the antibiotic discs. The diameter of the zone of inhibition was measured in millimeters using a Vernier caliper. The results were interpreted using the standards provided by the CLSI 2018.

Results and Discussion

Collection of Samples

Sample collection was done in the afternoon of October 23, 2018. The stalls that were used for sampling were within the street beside an elementary school. The stalls specifically sell only beverages and is stored in large plastic jars. The following were the samples collected for each stall: Gulaman (S1), Mango Juice (S2), and Buko Pandan (S3) from stall 1; Buko Juice (S4), Melon Juice (S5), and Milo (S6) from stall 2.

Isolation of Enterobacteriaceae

From the collected beverages, a total of 15 distinct colonies were isolated and later purified (Table 1). Two bacterial isolates were obtained from sample 1 (Gulaman) and sample 4 (Buko Juice). While four isolates were collected from sample 3 (Buko Pandan), three isolates were collected from sample 5 (Melon Juice) and sample 6 (Milo chocolate drink). On the other hand, only one was isolated from sample 2 (Mango Juice).

Table 1. Number of isolates collected from beverage samples

Beverage Name	Beverage Sample	Number of Isolates	Isolate Code
Gulaman	S1	2	S1-IS1 S1-IS2
Mango Juice	S2	1	S2-IS1
Buko Pandan	S3	4	S3-IS1A S3-IS1B S3-IS2A S3-IS2B
Buko Juice	S4	2	S4-IS1 S4-IS2
Melon Juice	S5	3	S5-IS1A S5-IS1B S5-IS2
Milo (Chocolate drink)	S6	3	S6-IS1A S6-IS1B

Legend: S1 – Gulaman, S2 – Mango Juice, S3 – Buko Pandan, S4 – Buko Juice, S5 – Melon Juice, S6 – Milo

The amount isolated is lower compared to other studies of Khan et al. (2015) which obtained between two to six isolates from their collection on fruit-based street beverages. Gaglio et al., (2017) explains that contaminated ice is a possible vector for transferring enteric bacteria, however, the risk may be lowered based on the different characteristics of the beverage: such as alcohol content, pH, CO₂ or antibacterial properties.

API20E for Microorganism Identification

All purified bacterial isolates (15) were tested first for oxidase reaction and were subjected for API 20E Identification. Based on the given test, all (100%) were oxidase negative (Table 2). Table 2 shows the identity of the different isolated bacteria. Most isolates (13) are from the Enterobacteriaceae family. The remaining two isolates: *Stenotrophomonas maltophilia* and *Acinetobacter baumannii / calcoaceticus* are from the Xanthomonadaceae and Moraxellaceae.

A total of nine (9) unique isolates were collected. *Raoultella planticola* was the most common isolated organism with a total of five isolates. It was isolated from Mango Juice, Buko Pandan, Buko Juice, and Melon Juice. The *Pantoea* genus was the second most isolated with a total of three (3) isolates. It was isolated from Melon Juice and Milo. Two isolates of *Enterobacter cloacae* were isolated from Gulaman and two isolates of *Serratia liquefaciens* was obtained from Buko Pandan. One isolate of *Stenotrophomonas maltophilia*, was obtained from Buko Juice. One isolate of *Acinetobacter baumannii / calcoaceticus* was isolated from Buko Juice. One isolate of *Enterobacter amnigenus 2* was obtained from Milo. The Oxidase test was performed to verify if the isolated bacteria were from the Enterobacter family which is an oxidase negative. As most of the result coincides with other studies where *Enterobacter*, *Raoultella*, *Pantoea*, and *Serratia* were isolated from different crops from a farm (Al-Kharousi et al., 2016; Leff & Fierer, 2013).

Table 2. Biochemical test results with identity using API 20E

Beverage Name	Beverage Sample	Number of Isolates	Isolate Code
Gulaman	S1-IS1	<i>Enterobacter cloacae</i> (97%)	Opportunistic Pathogen
	S1-IS2	<i>Enterobacter cloacae</i> (95.1%)	Opportunistic Pathogen
Mango Juice	S2-IS1	<i>Raoultella planticola</i> (100%)	Opportunistic Pathogen (Rare)
Buko Pandan	S3-IS1A	<i>Raoultella planticola</i> (100%)	Opportunistic Pathogen (Rare)
	S3-IS1B	<i>Raoultella planticola</i> (100%)	Opportunistic Pathogen (Rare)
	S3-IS2A	<i>Serratia liquefaciens</i> (86.7%)	Pathogenic
	S3-IS2B	<i>Serratia liquefaciens</i> (86.7%)	Pathogenic
Buko Juice	S4-IS1	<i>Stenotrophomonas maltophilia</i> (92.4%)	Pathogenic
	S4-IS2	<i>Raoultella planticola</i> (100%)	Opportunistic Pathogen (Rare)
Melon Juice	S5-IS1A	<i>Acinetobacter baumannii/calcoaceticus</i> (97.8%)	Opportunistic Pathogen
	S5-IS1B	<i>Pantoea spp 2</i> (80.7%)	Opportunistic Pathogen
	S5-IS2	<i>Raoultella planticola</i> (100%)	Opportunistic Pathogen (Rare)
Milo (Chocolate drink)	S6-IS1A	<i>Pantoea spp 3</i> (99.7%)	Opportunistic Pathogen
	S6-IS1B	<i>Pantoea spp 1</i> (98.3%)	Opportunistic Pathogen
	S6-IS2	<i>Enterobacter amnigenus 2</i> (84.6%)	Opportunistic Pathogen

Enterobacter cloacae is one of the most important species of the genus *Enterobacter*. It can be found that different environments such as from plants to humans. It is commonly found in hospitals, and it is considered as an opportunistic pathogen. It is known to cause lower respiratory tract infection, UTI, and meningitis. It may cause a wide range of infections, such as lower respiratory tract infections, urinary tract infections, and meningitis. Outbreaks usually occur in intensive care units, usually affecting patients with compromised immune systems. Its strains usually carry multiple antibiotic resistance genes which makes it clinically important (Liu et al., 2013).

Raoultella planticola is an encapsulated, nonmotile, aerobic, gram-negative, rod-shaped, and prevalent in environment with high amount of soil and water. Human cases come from a variety of sources; from immunocompromised conditions, seafood consumption, and interaction with soil or water. As of 2017, only 29 cases of infection have been reported which makes it a very rare human pathogen. It has been reported to cause bacteremia, conjunctivitis, pneumonia, UTI, and necrotizing fasciitis. Due to the limited data of it as a pathogen, there is little knowledge available regarding the mechanics of its pathogenicity. Due to its relatedness to the *Klebsiella* species, it is possible to have multi-drug resistant strains (Mehmood et al., 2018; Naganathan & Amin, 2018).

Serratia liquefaciens is an organism that is widely distributed in nature, it can be found in water, plants, fish, meat, pasteurized milk or cream. It has been rarely reported as a cause of nosocomial infections, such as UTI, pneumonia, post-sternotomy mediastinitis, neonatal meningitis, and septicemia from transfusion of contaminated blood (Mossad, 2000; Mahlen, 2011).

Pantoea is a genus that has species that are usually epiphytic or pathogenic with plants. However, there are also species that can be pathogenic to humans. One such species is the *P. agglomerans*, it is one of the species of *Pantoea* most commonly isolated from humans. It can be found in a variety of things such as from plants, soil, water, animals, and humans. It has been known to cause bacteremia due to contamination of intravenous fluid. Its antimicrobial resistance has been reported to be variable and further studies of its drug resistance patterns are needed, however, two studies have described it to be susceptible to antibiotics usually active on gram-negative bacilli (Büyükcam et al., 2018; Cruz, et al., 2007; Delétoile et al., 2009).

Stenotrophomonas maltophilia is a gram-negative aerobic bacillus commonly found in aquatic environments, soil, and plants. It is not part of the family *Enterobacteriaceae*, but part of the *Xanthomonadaceae* family. However, it is clinically important due to its status as an emerging multiple-drug-resistant organism. It has been described as an opportunistic pathogen, with infections occurring principally, but not exclusively, in individuals with compromised immune systems. It usually causes respiratory infection, and septicemia. Its infection is problematic due to the presence of many strains that may manifest resistance to multiple antibiotics (Brooke, 2012; Denton & Kerr, 1998; Looney et al., 2009; Pathmanathan & Waterer, 2005).

Acinetobacter is a pleomorphic aerobic gram-negative bacillus of the *Moraxellaceae* family. It is usually isolated in aquatic environments, and it is often cultured from a hospitalized patient's sputum, wounds, and urine. The most common infections causing species of it are *A. baumannii* and *A. calcoaceticus*. Outbreaks of it typically occur in intensive care units and immunocompromised patients. It has been known to cause bacteremia, meningitis, urinary tract infection (UTI), pneumonia and wound infections. It is known to survive for extended periods on the environmental surface, which leads to an increase of transmission within the health care setting. The capacity of the species to resist antibiotics may be due to its relatively impermeable outer membrane and its exposure to a large reservoir of resistant genes (Eliopoulos et al., 2008; Fishbain & Peleg, 2010; Kyriadikis et al., 2021).

Enterobacter amnigenus, like most of the members in the same family, is ubiquitous in nature. It has been isolated from soil, water, and various clinical specimens such as blood, feces, sputum, and wounds. The organism was known to cause sepsis and other infections. It is naturally susceptible or intermediate to many kinds of antibiotics, it is naturally resistant to benzylpenicillin, oxacillin, and macrolides (Stock & Wiedemann, 2002; Corti et al., 2007).

Kirby-Bauer Disc Diffusion Method

The 15 bacterial isolates were subjected to the antibiotic assay. Figure 1 shows the number of resistant isolates per antibiotic. The results for sensitivity of the isolates against the different groups of antibiotics using the standards set by CLSI 2018 can be seen in Table 3.

Figure 1. Relative abundance of resistance of the 15 isolates against the tested antibiotic

Table 3. Zones of inhibition of bacterial isolates for carbapenems and cephalosporins (III) (in mm)

Isolate Code	API20E Identity	Carbapenems		Cephalosporins (III)		
		MRP	ETP	C	CRO	CAZ
S1-IS1	<i>Enterobacter cloacae</i> (97%)	16.60 (R)	27.30 (S)	27.20 (S)	28.85 (S)	31.50 (S)
S1-IS2	<i>Enterobacter cloacae</i> (95.1%)	26.65 (S)	28.95 (S)	23.70 (S)	31.95 (S)	27.80 (S)
S2-IS1	<i>Raoultella planticola</i> (100%)	26.35 (S)	33.20 (S)	32.20 (S)	32.0 (S)	29.80 (S)
S3-IS1A	<i>Raoultella planticola</i> (100%)	21.95 (I)	29.0 (S)	29.0 (S)	32.80 (S)	27.35 (S)
S3-IS1B	<i>Raoultella planticola</i> (100%)	28.55 (S)	26.70 (S)	26.70 (S)	29.40 (S)	24.65 (S)
S3-IS2A	<i>Serratia liquefaciens</i> (86.7%)	25.45 (S)	30.50 (S)	26.50 (S)	29.50 (S)	26.20 (S)
S3-IS2B	<i>Serratia liquefaciens</i> (86.7%)	25.50 (S)	30.35 (S)	26.60 (S)	29.55 (S)	26.45 (S)
S4-IS1	<i>Stenotrophomonas maltophilia</i> (92.4%)	23.50 (S)	32.25 (S)	24.50 (S)	30.50 (S)	28.30 (S)
S4-IS2	<i>Raoultella planticola</i> (100%)	21.0 (I)	30.50 (S)	30.0 (S)	28.0 (S)	26.30 (S)
S5-IS1A	<i>Acinetobacter baumannii</i> / <i>calcoaceticus</i> (97.8%)	17.35 (I)	19.0 (S)	31.60 (S)	24.0 (I)	33.30 (S)
S5-IS1B	<i>Pantoea spp 2</i> (80.7%)	20.60 (S)	36.80 (S)	22.60 (S)	34.80 (S)	30.65 (S)
S5-IS2	<i>Raoultella planticola</i> (100%)	24.40 (S)	34.10 (S)	24.0 (S)	31.50 (S)	31.30 (S)
S6-IS1A	<i>Pantoea spp 3</i> (99.7%)	21.50 (S)	34.70 (S)	28.0 (S)	30.60 (S)	30.50 (S)
S6-IS1B	<i>Pantoea spp 1</i> (98.3%)	22.70 (S)	35.50 (S)	28.80 (S)	28.0 (S)	31.20 (S)
S6-IS2	<i>Enterobacter amnigenus 2</i> (84.6%)	25.75 (S)	38.80 (S)	27.0 (S)	28.30 (S)	31.50 (S)

Legend: S – Susceptible, I – Intermediate, R – Resistant, MRP – Meropenem, ETP – Ertapenem, C – Chloramphenicol, CRO – Ceftriaxone, CAZ – Ceftazidime

It can be seen in Figure 1 that the bacterial isolates were tested against Carbapenems and Third Generation Cephalosporins in which only one isolate (7%) were resistant to Meropenem. This isolate was identified to be *E. cloacae* (S1-IS1) using API 20E and was isolated from Gulaman. Three isolates were intermediate (20%); these were identified using API 20E as the *R. planticola* from Buko Pandan (S3-IS1A) and Buko Juice (S4-IS2); and the *A. baumannii* / *calcoaceticus* (S5-IS1A) from Melon Juice. The rest of the isolates (73%) are susceptible to it. Only one isolate (7%), which was identified as *A. baumannii* / *calcoaceticus* using API20E is intermediate against Ciprofloxacin. All the isolates (100%) are susceptible to Ertapenem, Chloramphenicol, and Ceftazidime. Carbapenems are broad spectrum antibiotics usually used as the last resort for seriously ill patients hospitalized in the intensive care units. Resistance against it is a global public-health problem. It presents a broad spectrum of antibacterial activity, proving to be the most effective beta-lactam against gram-positive and gram-negative bacteria. These also have less adverse effects and are safer to use compared to other last-line drugs (Jean et al., 2015).

Figure 1 also illustrates the resistance against different kinds of antibiotics. The bacterial isolates tested against Ampicillin: two isolates (13%) were susceptible to it; these are identified as the *Pantoea spp. 2* (S5-IS1) isolated from Melon Juice and the *Pantoea spp. 3* (S6-IS1A) isolated from Milo. The remaining 13 isolates (87%) are resistant to Ampicillin. There are four bacterial isolates (27%) that are resistant to Amoxicillin, with the remaining isolates (73%) susceptible to it. The bacteria, according to the API20E identification are *E. cloacae* from Gulaman (S1-IS1 and S1-IS2), and *S. liquefaciens* (S3-IS2A and S3-IS2B) from Buko Pandan. There are five isolates (33%) that are resistant to Trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole. These were identified as *R. planticola* from Mango juice (S2-IS1), Buko Pandan (S3-IS1A and S3-IS1B), Buko juice (S4-IS2), and Melon juice (S5-IS2). The remaining 10 isolates (67%) are susceptible. All isolates are susceptible to Tetracycline and Gentamicin.

E. cloacae (S1-IS1) is resistant to three different kinds of antibiotics: Meropenem, Ampicillin, and Amoxicillin. *E. cloacae* (S1-IS2) is resistant to two different kinds of antibiotics: Ampicillin, and Amoxicillin. *R. planticola* (S2-IS1) is resistant to two different kinds of antibiotics: Ampicillin and Trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole. *R. planticola* (S3-IS1A) is resistant to two different kinds of antibiotics: Ampicillin, and Trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole, it is also intermediate to Meropenem. *R. planticola* (S3-IS1B) is resistant to two different kinds of antibiotics: Ampicillin and Trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole. *S.*

liquefaciens (S3-IS2A and S3-IS2B) is resistant to two different kinds of antibiotics: Ampicillin and Amoxicillin. *S. maltophilia* (S4-IS1) is susceptible to all the tested antibiotics. *R. planticola* (S4-IS2) is resistant to two different kinds of antibiotics: Ampicillin and Trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole, as well as intermediate against Meropenem. *A. baumannii / calcoaceticus* (S5-IS1A) is resistant against Ampicillin; it is also intermediate against Meropenem and Ceftriaxone. *Pantoea spp. 2* (S5-IS1B) is susceptible to all the tested antibiotics. *R. planticola* (S5-IS2) is resistant to two different kinds of antibiotics: Ampicillin and Trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole. *Pantoea spp. 3* (S6-IS1A) is susceptible to all tested antibiotics. *Pantoea spp. 1* (S6-IS1B) is resistant to Ampicillin only. *E. amnigenus 2* (S6-IS2) is resistant to Ampicillin only. Counting intermediate as resistant; the isolates identified as *E. cloacae* (S1-IS1), *R. planticola* (S3-IS1A), *R. planticola* (S4-IS2), and *A. baumannii / calcoaceticus* (S5-IS1A) are resistant to three or more categories of antibiotics, which classifies them as multi-drug resistant bacteria (27%). Ampicillin is the most resisted antibiotic since it is a commonly used antibiotic. Over the past decade the antibiotic resistance of *Acinetobacter baumannii / calcoaceticus* has increased, which increases the difficulty of treating infections caused by the organism. XDR strains are present. They also possess a variety of intrinsic resistance mechanisms that may be expressed due to antimicrobial pressure. Its resistance may also be acquired through mutation and through contact with other antimicrobial resistant bacteria that inhabit similar environments (Blossom & Strinivasan, 2008; Howard et al., 2012). *R. planticola* was thought to be a low-virulence organism however, recently it is known to have a virulence capability like *K. pneumoniae*. Multidrug-resistant and carbapenem-resistant strains have emerged from different regions of the world. The results are like other studies where multi-drug resistant *R. planticola* were isolated, although it was isolated from clinical samples not beverage samples (Chen et al., 2014; Demiray et al., 2016).

Conclusion and Recommendations

Street beverages are widely sought after in the country since it is cheap, and it offers a quick refreshment against the heat. However, its sanitation and safety are not guaranteed, and it may contain different bacteria that may cause health problems to consumers. The beverage samples collected in Dasmariñas Bagong Bayan were used for collection. A total of 15 isolates were obtained from the beverage. Isolates were identified using API 20E and was subjected to antibiotic susceptibility assay using disc diffusion. It was learned that 27% of the bacterial isolates are multi-drug resistant. The isolates were identified using API 20E as *E. cloacae* (S1-IS1), *R. planticola* (S3-IS1A), *R. planticola* (S4-IS2), and *A. baumannii / calcoaceticus* (S5-IS1A). Infections caused by these antibiotic resistant bacteria are more dangerous since treatment options are limited compared to non-resistant bacteria, it will also cause a prolonged hospital stay which in turn increases the cost.

The following is recommended based on the result of the study:

1. Increase the size of the sampling area to multiple locations.
2. Determine the source of the isolate, if it was from the ice used, container, water, or the components of the beverage.
3. The use of molecular techniques like Polymerase Chain Reaction (PCR) for the determination of the identity and antimicrobial resistance of the isolates.
4. Determine the minimum inhibitory content (MIC) of antibiotics on the different isolates.
5. The use of Modified Hodge Test for the detection of Carbapenemases and Double-disc Synergy Method for the detection of ESBL production.

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